

An Analysis: The Effect of Different Barriers in Effective Communication

Author's Details:

- ⁽¹⁾ **Anila Solangi**-BS Scholar, Department of English, Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University, SBA
aneelasolangi45@gmail.com
- ⁽²⁾ **Jawaid Iqbal Mirani**-Lecturer, Department of English, Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University, SBA
javedmirani_nf@sbbusba.edu.pk
- ⁽³⁾ **Ayaz Ali Jarah**-Lecturer, Department of English, Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University, SBA
ayazali@sbbusba.edu.pk
- ⁽⁴⁾ **Misbah Memon**-BS Scholar, Department of English, Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University, SBA
misbahmemon200@gmail.com
- ⁽⁵⁾ **Abdul Razaque Lanjwani**-Lecturer, Department of English, Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University, SBA
abdul.razaque@sbbusba.edu.pk

Abstract

Sharing of ideas, thoughts, and information is considered as communication. In addition, when there is no sharing, there is no communication it means that sharing is necessary for every sort of communication. In communication process a barrier is which creates hurdle in conveying the message from the sender to the receiver. Further, the effective communication becomes flop due to different barriers at college, university and workplace. The purpose of this article is to discuss and understand various types of barriers which create problems in communication like Attitudinal Barriers, Behavioral Barriers, Cultural Barriers and Language Barriers. In addition, this paper also discusses important techniques to handle barriers in communication. The secondary data collection method has been utilized to gather data from journal, websites and books. Consequently, students, teachers, and scholars will find in this paper productive and helpful knowledge about barriers in communication and techniques to overcome barrier in communication.

Keywords: communication, barriers, attitudinal, behavioral, cultural, message

1. Introduction

Sharing of ideas, thoughts, and information is considered as communication. In addition, when there is no sharing, there is no communication it means that sharing is necessary for every sort of communication. In this way, message transferring is direct related to the process of communication in related environment. The barriers are the hurdles in the process of communication which create problems in effective communication. Further, these barriers resist the message to receive and to send by the sender and the receiver. In this regard, these barrier blocks, stop and create uneasy situation understating the message, thought, and ideas in class, organization and workplace. This paper will provide help to understand and recognize different barriers and how they effect on communication.

Most scholars are agree that communication is quite different form general talking in daily life. The communication is a simple process when two person exchange ideas and thoughts. Further, sender sends message with the concept that receiver would understand properly. On the other hand talking creates barriers during communication and resist effective message to reach to the receiver.

1.1 Objectives in the article

- To understand attitudinal and behavioral barriers in communication
- To understand cultural and language barriers in communication
- To discuss techniques of handle barriers in communication

1.2 Research Questions in the article

- What are the attitudinal and behavioral barriers in communication?
- What are the cultural and language barriers in communication?
- What are the techniques to handle barriers in communication?

2. Literature Review

Communication is two way process which involves sender and receiver. Further, effective communication becomes fail while different sorts of barriers occurs at education, business and workplace. Keyton (2011) mentions that specific communication process explains the quality of communication. Because effective communication provides positive results while ineffective provides negative results. Further, this process involves that encoded message should be understood properly by the decoder. It is only possible when sender uses simple language and proper medium for the communication.

Moreover, Tourish (2010) mentions that goof and successful communication depends upon the speaker's understanding of communication process successfully. Otherwise, receiver may face difficulties to comprehend the actual message. Such type of situation leads to the unsuccessful of communication.

Cheney (2011) argues that language barriers occur when same language is not used as medium of communication. Listeners usually get confused in such environment because spoken language is beyond understanding. In addition, he mentions that such situation can be handled with proper knowledge and understanding of the audience.

Rani (2016) gives details that cultural barriers are the result of speaker's incomplete information of audience like their beliefs, customs, education, nation and attitude. Further, it can be explained in this way that people work in multi-dimensional environment and speaker should not communicate such words that can be awkward to someone. It can lead flop communication and speaker will be considered successful.

Antos (2004) explains that usually communication process follows transmitting information from speaker and common understanding from listener. It means that the word common accepting of ideas of the speaker and the listener. Further, communication word acquired from "communis" word that recognized as a common speech. The exchanged information among people during communication that why communication is impossible without sharing information.

3. THE ATTITUDINAL AND BEHAVIORAL BARRIERS IN COMMUNICATION

Many studies mention that main cause of communication in schools, colleges, universities and workplace due to strange attitudes and behaviors. Brownell (2009) identify that carelessness, lack of knowledge becomes the cause of awkward behaviour and students avoid concentrating in the classroom. Addition, here are we through light on the reasons of attitudinal and behavioral barriers.

3.1 The Attitudinal Barriers

The communication becomes flop due to the different attitude, value, status and discrimination of the people at workplace, institution, class, university and an organization. In addition, person thinks that he/she should behave defiantly because of his position in the society and the community. In organization managers and supervisors think that they have complete authority on the subordinates and employees. They can allocate their duties, can give reward, promote and de-promote according to their choice but this can create barriers in organization. In this regard, attitude plays crucial role in the effective communication and individuals should not take negative control of power. Further, without judging people proper misunderstanding and discrimination might create. If someone values other it create positive environment of learning, working and cooperating. Because every individual possesses specific characteristics and others can get benefit from him/her with positive communication.

Fig 1: Divers individual characteristics

3.2 The Behavioural Barriers in Communication

The communication is effective process of exchanging information among people but weird behaviour create hurdles in communication. Behavioural barriers occur when we think we have knowledge about other people due to social and cultural background knowledge. In addition, we might be wrong and in this way stereotype observation is generated about the people. It creates barriers in at the workplace or any other situation and we should treat people as individual. If we broaden the communication procedure then we can reduce barriers in any environment.

4. THE CULTURAL AND LANGUAGE BARRIERS IN COMMUNICATION

When we communicate people with different background knowledge of their race, custom, culture, and tradition it means we obtain different knowledge about their habits, values, and beliefs. Previous knowledge and experience assist us to understand people culture and values.

4.1 The Cultural Barriers

People communicate according their culture and it is suitable to avoid barriers in commutation place. Cultural barriers occurs due lack of knowledge of caste, tradition, way of living, dressing and area of living. Prior knowledge assist us to understand people culture and values. There are multiple techniques to understand people or to create empathy. Here we mention some of them:

- Give value people's ideas and feelings
- Giving suitable advice to the people
- Motivating people to face every situation
- Respect every culture, tradition and language
- By adopting you attitude

4.2 The Language Behaviour

In colleges, universities and workplace verbal communication barriers occur when individuals usually fail to comprehend the identical spoken utterance. This type of barriers also occurs when speaker have high level of language abilities like speaking, fluency, vocabulary and listener posses low level of understanding. For instance:

At university in the classroom due to English language the students might face problems to understand the lecture properly. Due to this barrier the students would not prefer to respond to the teacher.

Moreover, language is key and appropriate channel of communication. If the speaker wants to avoid language barrier he/she should use easy and simple language and sometimes he/she should use listeners' language to make communication effective. Consequently, listeners would respond quickly and participate in the classroom effectively.

5 SOME TECHNIQUES TO HANDLE BARRIERS DURING COMMUNICATION

For human language is main source of communication. It should use effectively to make communication useful. Skillful speakers utilize various techniques to make their communication effective and listeners motivate from such speakers. Here we discuss some useful techniques if speaker uses them he/she can avoid every sort of barrier at workplace or environment. These techniques are:

- Communicative environment should be friendly and stress free.
- Speaker should always motivate the listeners so that they become ready to participate.
- Speaker should use simple and easy language so the listener should understand along with language speaker should use effective non-verbal symbols and signs to make communication understandable.
- Speaker should take effective help from technology like multi-media during communication. Because audio-visual process of communication is more effective and understandable as compare to only spoken method.
- Speaker should converse with appropriate volume because voice, accent and pitch perform significant function in the communication.
- Environment should be relaxed and comfortable so that listener feel relax to participate in provided communication environment.

6 Conclusion

Exchanging of information is considered as a communication. In addition, no sharing, no communication it means that sharing is necessary for every sort of communication. Moreover, it becomes obligatory for the students, teachers, and even for common people to comprehend the communication method for both personal and professional levels. The multiple methods of communication through people can communicate. In addition each method has specific purpose to fulfill. Different barrier create different hurdle for the communication and speaker should possess skills to recognize those barriers. He must to how to control such barriers and he should utilize useful techniques to overcome these barriers. Consequently, speaker will be able to transfer efficiently and listener will be capable to comprehend the message easily.

References

- i. Rani, K. U. (2016). *Communication Barriers*. *Veda's Journal of English Language and Literature*, 3(2), 74-76
- ii. Keyton, J. (2011). *Communication and organizational culture: A key to understanding work experience*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- iii. Cheney, G. (2011). *Organizational communication in an age of globalization: Issues, reflections, practices*. Long Grove, IL: Waveland Press.
- iv. Canary, H. (2011). *Communication and organizational knowledge: Contemporary issues for theory and practice*. Florence, KY: Taylor & Francis.
- v. Tourish, D. (2010). *Auditing organizational communication: A handbook of research, theory, and practice*. New York, NY: Routledge.
- vi. Luthans, F. (2009) *Organizational Behaviour*, McGraw-Hill, New Delhi.
- vii. Antos, G. (2004). *Handbook of interpersonal communication*. The Hague, the Netherlands: Mouton De Gruyter.